

THE IMPORTANCE OF FOLKLORE SONGS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL PERFORMANCE

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Abstract. In the article, information is given about the introduction of the song genre in the life of the society, its role in the way of human life, its expression in the structure of folk traditions, customs, ceremonies, and holidays in the development of folk art.

Keywords. Mixed, personality, thinking, synthetic, primitive, ancient, belief, mythological, zmpirical, imagination, rituals, ritual.

Musical folklore - human speech, the ancient types and genres of the folk oral artistic creation began to emerge in a mixed manner. These synthetic creations, which include various forms of human artistic thought , are closely connected with all aspects of primitive human life and activity, and reflect the religious beliefs and mythological views of ancient people, basic scientific, i.e. empirical knowledge, perceptions of nature and society. However, such examples of ancient folklore have not reached us, but their traces and some parts were recorded in various ideas and views related to the people's living and lifestyle, in the structure of folk traditions, customs, ceremonies, holidays, in some written sources, in later periods. preserved only as remnants in folklore works.

The song is the interpreter of the human soul. He sings from cradle to grave. He expresses his heart's content with a song. In his sad days and in his happy days, he sings, sings, and creates songs. It is said that Allah brought the soul into the human body through singing. Therefore, his whole lifestyle and life found its reflection in songs. People's life, national customs, values and traditions are expressed in all their aspects and charms in the songs. People's thinking, worldview and unique nature are embodied in the songs.

In Uzbek folklore, the analysis of the song genre, its extremely rich artistic flair, and expressiveness have been studied by many of our researchers. Most of them were recorded and became our spiritual heritage. Especially in this field, the variety of song genres of Uzbek national songwriters Muzayyaia Alaviya, doctor of philological sciences, professors T.Mirzaev, M.Joraev, doctor of philological sciences D.Oraeva A.Musokulov, scientist R.Nosirov, researcher N.Ortiqmatov and others, lyrical melody, poetic features are thoroughly analyzed. The publication of a collection of Uzbek folk songs called "Shoda-shoda marvarid" by the well-known scientist Ergash Ochilov is also one of the great achievements. Also, great importance is attached to the study and research of Uzbek folk songs, which are the basis of our folklore studies. In particular, Professor O. Safarov's "Happy wedding "Yor-Yor" included in the work "Yor-Yor" and the songs related to the wedding ceremony, "Bukhorcha" and "Mavrigi" songs were added as a significant contribution. The poetic contents of the series unique to Bukhara, the historical genetic basis of the series, performance methods and compositional features are skillfully interpreted in the book . In addition, the book "Uzbek Folk Music" published by Academician Yu.Rajabi collected folk songs and terms. The successful part of the book is that it is recognized that the genre of Uzbek folk songs is rich in terms of composition, and the recorded songs and terms are divided into groups specific to the theme of the genre. The work of folk songs, li In addition to ric, wedding, satirical and humorous songs, mourning songs, seasonal songs, modern and moral songs, children's folklore prayers, songs in the

genre of advice are also examples of new types of songs.

The unique richness of the song is its extreme richness in artistic content and visual means. The verses in them are distinguished from other genres by their wealth of meaningful expressions, fragments and artistic tools, and by being imprinted in a person's heart. People's spirit, people's depth and creativity are especially visible. Scarf, handkerchief, ring, thorn, snake, flower, nightingale, apple, tulip in songs. There are artistic pictorial tools such as river and horse, each of which acquires a symbolic meaning. For example, a handkerchief is a symbol of love and affection. A lover giving a handkerchief to a lover means building a life with him, agreeing to be together. But the highest dream for a lover. The battle of life and death is won. The symbol of the handkerchief also represents this symbol in written literature. In Alisher Navoi's ghazal, in the form of a handkerchief , he artistically expresses that the sorrows, love and loyalty of a lover are embodied in the threads of each stanza :

Get fat, my dear, if you sew, take my needle,
Make my soul a bond of embroidery.

The lyrical songs of the Uzbek people are distinguished by their colorful artistic means. Each phrase in it , simile, repetition, rhythm, enlivenment, qualification, and symbol, acts as a concrete fragment in expressing the picture of various experiences of the individual's psyche. For example, the simile in the famous song "Sunbula" is forever imprinted in the mind of every child . This - arrow can be a salve for any lover's day, burning in the fire of farewell:

If there is in this world
Whole heart.
Making an oven out of paper,
Make firewood out of flowers.
May flowers be planted in your step!

It is clear that as long as a person lives in this world, if he gains something, he will lose something. In the layer of happiness , some feelings of unhappiness

are hidden, that is, wasted energy, sadness, pain, regret , and dreams. Happiness is given to a person at the cost of these losses. It is a condition of life. The truth of life that one cannot achieve complete happiness without loss is vividly expressed through this simile, just as a stove can never be made out of paper, and a flower can never serve as firewood. The image of an apple is often found in songs, and the apple is also a symbol of love between lovers in folklore. More precisely, it is a symbol of a family, a dream of having children:

From the delicacy of the apple,
It looks grainy.
Dew fell on the leaf,
I am his devan,

The delicacy of the apple is that it is very difficult to preserve love, to achieve it, and to find a suitable partner is a vital problem, and its grain is to achieve a great blessing like a child, which is even greater happiness. Shabnam is the purity and innocence of the path to happiness. Wisdom is to own this effort.

The art of repetition occupies a special place in songs. These repetitions are often used in words, exclamations, verses and refrains, and each of them performs a specific poetic function:

oh my brother
Prepare my eyes.
It made my skin yellow
This pencil is a brow-bow

Similes in the verses , i.e. ukajon - very closeness , kuralai - eyes as beautiful as the eyes of a child, yellow color - hajr, the exclamation " hey " out of the pain of separation - served to further intensify the passions in this feeling.

There is a lot of repetition in songs. The essence of this is yor-yor - the wedding ceremony. The phrase associated with this ritual is one of the traditional types of repetition, which plays an important role in creating rhythmic musicality in songs:

They say cut your eyebrows
 Black-eyed brother, yor-yor.
 Sweet words my brother, yor-yor,
 Show me your eyebrow
 My dear brother- hey.yor -yor.

In our time, the interest in performing folk songs has increased. They are sung in folk tunes, pop genres and folk songs. Especially People's Artist of Uzbekistan Farrukh Zokirov, Yulduz Usmanova, Ozodbek Nazarbekov. National Uzbek songs in the repertoire of artists such as Gulsanam Mamazoitova, Hosi la Rakhimova, Khurshid Rasulov, who have served the republic, are popular with our people.

A song is a poetic-musical genre in a broad sense, the most popular type of vocal music, based on a more busy form, as well as a general expression of poetic works intended for singing. Songs belonging to folk art, created by composers and composers, in the direction of popular music are distinguished. Depending on the origin, genre and content, ceremonial songs, public songs, urban, peasant, children's, household, military, lyrical, dance and other songs are distinguished. The song is distinguished by the compactness of the lower range, the musical development based on the form of stanza or stanza-refrain, the commonality of word and melody intonations in the system of tones, the development of the ideological-emotional content of the poetic text is generally expressed as an artistic end. Another unique aspect of the song is the mutual proportionality of the poetic text and the melody forms, the structures of the same volume are based on verse-stanza, melody-period. The poetic texts of the song are distinguished by their clear composition and the expression of a certain complete thought in each verse. In the East, folk songs have their own national characteristics, and in Central Asia they are called ir (jir), terma, olan, lapar, yalla. On the basis of these, the creativity of composers, modern song forms developed in the 20th century. In European professional music, poet-singers of the Middle Ages, troupers and

troubadours in France, works of minnesingers in Germany, examples of the art of meisterzingers, polyphonic Italian canzonetta created during the Renaissance, German Lied, French chanson, songs in the homophonic style popularized in the XVII-XVIII centuries, composers of the Romantic period The song in his work is the stage of development of mass song, pop songs and other professional songs that have developed widely in the 20th century. Among the poets P. Beranje, R. Burns, R. Hamzatov, V. Vysotsky and others, in Uzbekistan Hamza, Habibi, Sabir Abdulla, Mirtemir, Chustiy, T. Tola, P. Momin, N. Narzullaev, Muhammad Yusuf, E. Vokhidov, J. Jabborov and others have made great contributions to the development of song poetry.

In the narrow sense, a song is a genre of Uzbek folk music , beginning with a double rhyme, usually sung with 7-8 finger-weighted quatrains, and a busy form of expression. Captions of the first quatrain aaaa. can be in the ratio aava, aavv or aavs. In Uzbek songs, the first verse usually consists of a combination of four poetic verses and relative complete melodic structures that are the basis of their singing. The number of melodic structures is 2-4, and their interrelationships consist of such means as repeating the main sentence, changing it, or ending it with a new sentence that is developed to a certain extent. Uzbek songs, in contrast to chants, are mostly in the fifth-sixth range in a small voice, and sometimes they are performed with circle accompaniment. Kuychan melodious songs are found mainly in samples with a lyrical theme. In other songs, there are long melodies that have a melancholic quality, but they appear more towards the end of the song. Although special individual refrains are almost never used in the songs, sometimes there are repeated words that serve as small refrains, as well as the use of exclamatory phrases such as "john", "yor", "dod-ey". From the point of view of genre, songs belonging to the work of 20th century Uzbek composers and especially composers have undergone certain changes, incorporating characteristics of other genres, including lapar, yalla, ashula, terma. In particular, you can see band-chorus structures, percussion instruments, and dance forms in

them. Among the Uzbek composers Yu. Rajabi, K. Jabborov, Fakhridin Sodikov, T. Jalilov, G'. Toshmatov, N. Khasanov, M. Mirzaev, B. Aliev, R. Tursunov and others, from the composers T. Sodikov, M. Burhonov, M. Leviev, S. Yudakov, A. Otajonov, F. Nazarov, A. Nazarov, F. Alimov, K. Komilov, for children A. Mukhamedov, E. Schwartz, Il. Akbarov, N. Norkhojaev, Anvar Ergashev, A. Mansurov , Sh.Ramazonov, Ik.Akbarov, E.Solikhov, D.Omonullaeva, A.Rasulov and others in the pop music genre have created significant works in the song genre.

Learning Uzbek folk songs is an example of our boundless love and respect for our national culture. Each song is considered the creativity of our people and is an incomparable treasure added to the ocean of our high spirituality.

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